

Seebeck–Peltier Transition Approach to Oncogenesis

Umberto Lucia ^{*,†}

Dipartimento Energia “Galileo Ferraris”, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino, Italy; giulia.grisolia@polito.it

* Correspondence: umberto.lucia@polito.it; Tel.: +39-011-090-4558

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

Received: 12 September 2020; Accepted: 12 October 2020; Published: 14 October 2020

Abstract: In this paper, a non-equilibrium thermodynamic approach to cancer is developed. The thermo-electric effects in the cell membrane are analysed, in relation to the Seebeck-like and the Peltier-like effects. The role of the cell membrane electric potential is studied from a thermodynamic viewpoint, pointing out the relation between the proliferation rate and the membrane potential, the existence of a thermodynamic threshold for the mitotic activity, the relation between metastases and membrane potential and the comprehension of the role of ions fluxes in the cell behaviour.

Keywords: membrane electric potential; heat flux; ions fluxes; cancer; non-equilibrium thermodynamics

1. Introduction

Living cells membrane presents different permeability related to specific ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , Ca^{2+} , etc.), which generate an electric potential difference $\Delta\phi$, between the cytoplasm and the extracellular environment, in relation to the environment itself [1]. A cell is defined as depolarized if its electric potential difference is relatively less negative in relation to the normal value of a living cell, which, on the contrary, is defined as hyperpolarised because it is more negative.

The membrane electric potential is evaluated by the Goldman–Hodgkin–Katz equation, which allows us to express $\Delta\phi$ as a function of the permeability P , the concentrations of ions, at the both side of the membrane and the temperature [2,3]. Moreover, it was pointed out how intercellular communications can also modify the membrane electric potential [1].

Since 1956, it emerged that cancer cells are electrically different from the normal cells [4]. In 1969, Cone Jr. highlighted that a hyperpolarisation state characterises the start of the M phase of the cell cycle, and he introduced the hypothesis of a possible relation between the cell cycle progression and the membrane electric potential changes [5]. Moreover, in 1970, he pointed out how the membrane hyperpolarisation could block reversibly the synthesis of DNA and mitosis [6]. Last, in 1971, generalising the experimental results, a lowered membrane potential was identified as a cause of an increase in proliferation of the cancer cells, in relation to the normal ones [7]. Until now, all of these results have always been confirmed [8–12].

The molecular organisation and electrical properties of the living cell membranes act as a diffusion barrier between the cytoplasm and the external medium. The cell membrane is a bi-molecular film of lipid molecules, in which are embedded functional proteins, used by the cell for a great number of functions, including energy transduction, signalling, transport of ions, etc. [13]. Recently, the fundamental role played by electrostatic interactions between macroions in aqueous electrolyte solutions has been highlighted [14], with particular regard to soft matter, interface physics and chemistry, biophysics and biochemistry, etc. The presence of macroions affects the distribution of the small mobile ions in the electrolyte, because their counterions are attracted to the macroion surface, while the coions are repelled from the macroion surface [14], with the result of generating the electric

double layer [14–19]. The analytical and numerical models for the analysis and description of the structure and energy of the electric double layer have represented a fundamental development in the comprehension of their properties [14,20–31] also in relation to their application in medicine and biophysics. Concepts like charge neutrality, Debye length and double layer have been proven to be very useful to explain the electrical properties of a cellular membrane [32].

In the last years, the role of the membrane electric potential has been shown also in the control of the fundamental cell functions, such as proliferation, migration and differentiation [33–35]. In this context, many experimental evidences pointed out significant depolarisation during malignant transformation of normal cells [36,37], due to an increase of Na⁺ intracellular concentration in tumour, in relation to the normal cells. The intracellular concentration of K⁺ seems to maintain approximately the same values [38].

As a consequence of the previous results, some questions arose:

- The relation between the proliferation rate and the membrane potential.
- The possible existence of a threshold for the mitotic activity.
- The possible relation between metastases and membrane potential.
- The comprehension of the role of ions fluxes in the cell behaviour.

The aim of this paper was to develop a non-equilibrium thermodynamic analysis of the membrane electric potential, recently published in Ref. [39], in order to suggest a new approach to respond to these questions, by considering the link between ions and heat fluxes.

2. Materials and Methods

The membrane potential of a living cell can be evaluated by using the modified Goldman–Hodgkin–Katz equation [2,3]:

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{P_{Na^+}[Na^+]_{outside} + P_{K^+}[K^+]_{outside} + P_{Cl^-}[Cl^-]_{outside}}{P_{Na^+}[Na^+]_{inside} + P_{K^+}[K^+]_{inside} + P_{Cl^-}[Cl^-]_{inside}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where [A] is the concentration of the ion A, $R = 8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ is the universal constant of ideal gasses, T is the absolute temperature, F is the Faraday constant and P is the relative permeability such that $P_{Na^+} = 0.04$, $P_{K^+} = 1$ and $P_{Cl^-} = 0.45$.

Our aim was to introduce a non-equilibrium thermodynamic approach; therefore, we must use the general phenomenological relations [40–42]:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{J}_e = -L_{11} \frac{\nabla\phi}{T} - L_{12} \frac{\nabla T}{T^2} \\ \mathbf{J}_Q = -L_{21} \frac{\nabla\phi}{T} - L_{22} \frac{\nabla T}{T^2} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{J}_e is the current density [A m^{-2}], \mathbf{J}_Q is the heat flux [W m^{-2}], T is the living cell temperature and L_{ij} are the phenomenological coefficients, such that [42] $L_{12} = L_{21}$ in absence of magnetic fields, and $L_{11} \geq 0$ and $L_{22} \geq 0$, and [42] $L_{11}L_{22} - L_{12}^2 > 0$.

At the stationary state, the net ion fluxes is null, $\mathbf{J}_e = \mathbf{0}$, so the previous equations hold to:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\nabla T}{T} = -\frac{L_{11}}{L_{12}} \nabla\phi \\ \mathbf{J}_Q = \left(L_{22} \frac{L_{11}}{L_{12}} - L_{12} \right) \frac{\nabla\phi}{T} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In relation to the first equation, it is possible to highlight that a Seebeck-like effect occurs in the cell membrane [39], while the other equation expresses an analytical, but also biophysical, relation between the heat flux towards the environment and the membrane electric potential gradient. Considering that:

$$\dot{Q} = \int_A \mathbf{J}_Q \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dA \tag{4}$$

where A is the area of the membrane external surface, we can write:

$$\delta\dot{Q} = \left(L_{22} \frac{L_{11}}{L_{12}} - L_{12} \right) \frac{\nabla\phi}{T} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dA = \frac{k}{T} \nabla\phi \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dA \tag{5}$$

where $k = (L_{22}L_{11}/L_{12}) - L_{12}$ is a thermoelectric property of the cell, which links the heat flux to the membrane electric gradient. Equation (5) relates the heat power, exchanged with the cell environment, to the cell membrane potential gradient.

Cells exchange heat power with their environment by convection [43]:

$$\delta\dot{Q} = \rho c \frac{dT}{dt} dV = -\alpha (T - T_0) dA \tag{6}$$

where $\rho \approx 10^3 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ is the cell density, $c \approx 4186 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is the specific heat of the cell, $\alpha \approx 0.023 Re^{0.8} Pr^{0.35} \lambda / \langle R \rangle$ is the coefficient of convection, with $\lambda \approx 0.6 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ conductivity, $Re \approx 0.2$ the Reynolds number and $Pr \approx 0.7$ the Prandtl number [43], A area of the cell membrane, V is the cell volume and $\langle R \rangle = dV/dA \approx V/A$ is the mean radius of the cell. So, it follows that:

$$\frac{d\phi}{d\ell} = - \frac{\alpha}{\left(L_{22} \frac{L_{11}}{L_{12}} - L_{12} \right)} T (T - T_0) = - \frac{\alpha}{k} T (T - T_0) \tag{7}$$

which highlights the relation between the membrane gradient of the membrane electric potential and the temperature of the cell, being ℓ the length of the membrane.

If the ion fluxes persists to be null, the cell cannot develop biochemical reaction to sustain the cell life [39,44]; consequently, $\mathbf{J}_e \neq 0$, so [40,41]:

$$\frac{dc_i}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i \tag{8}$$

where c_i is the concentration of the i -th ion (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , etc.), t is the time and \mathbf{J}_i is the current density of the i -th ion. Therefore, using Equation (2), it follows [40,41]:

$$\frac{d\phi}{dT} = - \frac{L_{21}}{L_{11}} \frac{1}{T} \tag{9}$$

which allows us to point out that a Peltier-like effect occurs, a temperature variation is caused by the variation of the membrane electric potential, as a consequence of the ions fluxes, and a related heat flux is generated [40,41,45]:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_u \tag{10}$$

Consequently, the specific entropy rate can be obtained as follows [46–48]:

$$T \frac{ds}{dt} = \nabla \cdot \left(\mathbf{J}_u - \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i \mathbf{J}_i \right) - \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{J}_i \cdot \nabla \mu_i \tag{11}$$

where s is the specific entropy, T is the temperature and μ is the chemical potential. $\mathbf{J}_S = \mathbf{J}_u - \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i \mathbf{J}_i$ is the contribution of the inflows and outflows, and $T\sigma = -\sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{J}_i \cdot \nabla \mu_i$ is the dissipation function [40]. We can highlight that diffusion is caused by the gradient of the chemical potential:

$$\mu_i = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i} \right)_{T,p,n_{k \neq i}} \tag{12}$$

where G is the Gibbs energy, n is the number of moles and p is the pressure. Until now, we have considered a flux in accordance with the concentration gradient. In the case of fluxes against the concentration gradients, it is possible to introduce [40,41]:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = - \sum_{k=1}^N L_{ik} \nabla \mu_k \tag{13}$$

together with the Gibbs–Duhem relation [41]:

$$\nabla \mu_N = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \frac{c_i}{c_N} \nabla \mu_i \tag{14}$$

Consequently, Onsager’s reciprocity relations are not satisfied, but, if we consider:

$$\mathcal{L}_{ik} = L_{ik} - \frac{c_i}{c_N} L_{iN} \tag{15}$$

where \mathcal{L} are the real measurable quantities, it is possible to obtain [40]:

$$\mathbf{J}_i = - \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} \mathcal{L}_{ik} \nabla \mu_k \tag{16}$$

with $\mathcal{L}_{ik} = \mathcal{L}_{ki}$ and

$$T\sigma = - \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \mathbf{J}_i \cdot \nabla \mu_i \tag{17}$$

The entropy outflow is fundamental in order to generate order from disorder [49], as Schrödinger himself pointed out [44].

3. Results

In this paper, we have developed a non-equilibrium thermodynamic analysis of the cell membrane electric potential in order to explain, analytically, the role of the ions fluxes in relation to cancer behaviour, but also to the thermoelectric properties of the membrane itself. Indeed, the Equation (7) allows us to state that an increase in the cell temperature (development of any inflammation) implies a decrease in the membrane electric potential.

Always in relation to Equation (7), we can highlight that the values of α , T and T_0 are approximately the same for cancer and normal cells; therefore, from a physical viewpoint, the difference between cancer and normal cells must be expressed in terms of the thermoelectric coefficient k . In particular, experimental results point out that the membrane of cancer cells is depolarized [1,12]; consequently, in relation to our Equation (7), the thermoelectric coefficient for cancer results greater than the one of a normal cell.

Moreover, during its life cycle, cell membranes have continue transitions between Seebeck-like and Peltier-like effects to sustain heat and mass fluxes. These continuous transitions are the thermo-electric cycle responsible for respiration, metabolism, reorganisation, proliferation, communication and all the biophysical and biochemical processes inside the cells [39].

During the Seebeck-like effect, the membrane exchanges heat towards the environment, with a related decrease in its entropy, in accordance with the Schrödinger approach. During the Peltier-like effect, the membrane exchanges ions, metabolites and waste molecules with the environment in order to realise the biochemical processes for life and proliferation.

Here, we develop a numerical evaluation in relation to the Ca^{2+} -flux. This example is very important due to the fundamental role played by the Ca^{2+} ion in the regulation of a great number of cell functions [50–54].

To do so, we write the Equation (11) as follows:

$$T \frac{ds}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{J}_u - \mu_{\text{Ca}} \mathbf{J}_{\text{Ca}}) \quad (18)$$

This last equation, considering T constant, and following Prigogine ($ds/dt = 0$) [55], becomes

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{J}_u - \mu_{\text{Ca}} \mathbf{J}_{\text{Ca}}) = 0 \quad (19)$$

Now, we introduce the First Law of Thermodynamics for the cell membrane, so we can write [50]

$$\frac{du}{dt} dV = \rho c \frac{dT}{dt} dV = \delta \dot{Q} = -\alpha (T - T_0) dA \quad (20)$$

where $\rho \approx 10^3 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ is the cell density, $c \approx 4186 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is the specific heat of the cell, $\alpha \approx 0.023 Re^{0.8} Pr^{0.35} \lambda / \langle R \rangle$ is the coefficient of convection, with $\lambda \approx 0.6 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ conductivity, $Re \approx 0.2$ the Reynolds number and $Pr \approx 0.7$ the Prandtl number [43], A area of the cell membrane, V is the cell volume and $\beta = \alpha dA/dV$ is constant. Now, considering Equation (10), we can write:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_u = \alpha \frac{dA}{dV} (T - T_0) \quad (21)$$

and, it follows [50]:

$$\nabla \cdot (\mu_{\text{Ca}} \mathbf{J}_{\text{Ca}}) = \frac{\delta \dot{Q}}{dV} = \alpha \frac{dA}{dV} (T - T_0) \quad (22)$$

$$J_{\text{Ca}} = \frac{\ell \cdot \alpha}{\mu_{\text{Ca}} \cdot \langle R \rangle} (T - T_0) = \frac{4 \times 10^{-9} \times 0.023 \times 0.2^{0.8} \times 0.7^{0.35} \times 0.6 \times 0.4}{-552.79 \times 10^3 \cdot \langle R \rangle^2} = \frac{-0.97 \times 10^{-17}}{\langle R \rangle^2} [\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}] \quad (23)$$

where $\ell \approx 0.004 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ is the depth of the cell membrane [56] and $\langle R \rangle$ is the mean radius of the cell, considered, in the first approximation, as a sphere, $\mu_{\text{Ca}} = -552.79 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $T - T_0 \approx 0.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [57]. The numerical result depends on the mean size of the cell. Considering that the mean radius for a human cell is of the order of 10^{-6} – 10^{-5} m , it follows that the Ca^{2+} -flux is of the order of 21 – $450 \text{ mmol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$, which can be expressed as $\sim 0.010 \text{ mol s}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$, in agreement with the experimental results obtained in [58].

Now, we can evaluate the electric field at the living cell membrane. The electric potential at the membrane is of the order of 10 – 100 mV . The thickness of the membrane is of the order of $0.004 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Consequently, the electric field of the living cell membrane is of the order of 10^7 – 10^8 V m^{-1} . Therefore, for the Ca^{2+} fluxes, the power generated by the fluxes through the membrane electric fields results in:

$$\dot{W}_{el,\text{Ca}} = J_{\text{Ca}} \cdot \mathcal{N} \cdot 2e \cdot E \cdot 4\pi \langle R \rangle^2 \quad (24)$$

where $\mathcal{N} = 6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $e = 1.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$ is the value of the elementary electric charge, 2 is the valence of the Calcium and E is the electric field. Therefore, the power results are of the order of $(2.4 \times 10^{-4}$ – $2.4 \times 10^{-3}) \text{ [W]}$.

As a consequence of these results, we are able to propose the following responses to the questions introduced in the previous section:

- The relation between the proliferation rate and the membrane potential can be explained by the modification of the cytosolic proteins functions due to phosphorylation or dephosphorylation, related to the hydrolysis of ATP necessary for the coupled ion along its electrochemical gradient.
- The possible existence of a threshold for the mitotic activity is shown in Equation (7), which presents a thermal threshold ($T > T_0$) for the cell membrane electric potential gradient, which has been experimentally shown to be related to the mitotic activity.
- The possible relation between metastases and membrane potential can be explained by considering that the metastasis is related to the ability of the cell to move through the intercellular space, but this ability is related to the water outflow and the Ca^{2+} - K^+ channel activation, related to the hyperpolarisation of the membrane itself.
- The comprehension of the role of ions fluxes in the cell behaviour can be explained by considering that the depolarization was experimentally shown to be a characteristic of cancer, and our approach highlights just the differences in the thermo-electric properties of the cell membrane in cancer and normal cells.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

A decrease of Cl^- intracellular concentration has been showed to be directly linked to malignant proliferation [12], and a decrease of Na^+ intracellular concentration is able to hyperpolarise the cell membrane, with a determinant consequence on the mitotic arrest [12,51–54,59–72]. Hyperpolarisation determines an activation of the Ca^{2+} - K^+ channel which increases the Ca^{2+} intracellular concentration [12,73], with the consequence that the Ca^{2+} - K^+ channel results a fundamental controller of the membrane electric potential. In this context, also water outflow was shown to play a fundamental role in metastasis activity [12,74].

Proteins play a fundamental role in ion transport. Proteins in the cytosolic can be modified in their functions by phosphorylation or dephosphorylation. An ion actively crosses the membrane against its electrochemical potential, whereby the necessary energy is derived either from the hydrolysis of ATP, or from the movement of a co-transported, or coupled ion along its electrochemical gradient. In this context, the role played by the H^+ -ATPase is fundamental, because it moves positive charges into the cell, while it generates large membrane voltage (inside negative and outside positive) and a pH gradient [75–78]. Protein phosphorylation is an important cellular regulatory mechanism, because many enzymes and receptors [50,79,80] are activated or deactivated by phosphorylation by involving kinases and phosphatases. Moreover, kinases are responsible for cellular transduction signalling [81–84].

In this paper, the theoretical explanation of the ions role in relation to the cell membrane potential has been obtained by introducing the non-equilibrium thermodynamic approach. It is the first fundamental step for a new approach in cancer researches. Indeed, it highlights:

- The relation between cell membrane potential and temperature.
- The relation between cell membrane potential and ions fluxes.
- The spontaneous symmetry breaking in the Onsager relations as a fundamental transition between the Seebeck-like effect and the Peltier-like effect in the cell membrane.
- The link between life and the transition from a Seebeck-like effect to a Peltier-like effect and viceversa.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, U.L.; methodology, U.L. and G.G.; software, G.G.; validation, U.L. and G.G.; formal analysis, U.L.; investigation, G.G.; resources, U.L.; data curation, G.G.; writing—original draft preparation, U.L. and G.G.; writing—review and editing, U.L. and G.G.; visualization, G.G.; supervision, U.L.; project administration, U.L.; funding acquisition, U.L. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Yang, M.; Brackenbury, W.J. Membrane potential and cancer progression. *Front. Physiol.* **2013**, *4*, 185. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Goldman, D.E. Potential impedance, and rectification in membranes. *J. Gen. Physiol.* **1943**, *27*, 37–60. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
3. Hodgkin, A.L.; Katz, B. The effect of sodium ions on the electrical activity of giant axon of the squid. *J. Physiol.* **1949**, *108*, 37–77. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
4. Ambrose, E.J.; James, A.M.; Lowick, J.H. Differences between the electrical charge carried by normal and homologous tumour cells. *Nature* **1956**, *177*, 576–577. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
5. Cone, C.D. Electroosmotic interactions accompanying mitosis initiation in sarcoma cells. *Vitr. Trans. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* **1969**, *31*, 404–427. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Cone, C.D. Variation of the transmembrane potential level as a basic mechanism of mitosis control. *Oncology* **1970**, *24*, 438–470. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Cone, C.D. Unified theory on the basic mechanism of normal mitotic control and oncogenesis. *J. Theor. Biol.* **1971**, *30*, 151–181. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Tokuoka, S.; Marioka, H. The membrane potential of the human cancer and related cells (I). *Gann* **1957**, *48*, 353–354.
9. Altman, P.L.; Katz, D. *Biological Handbook Vol. 1: Cell Biology*; Federation of American Society for Experimental Biology: Bethesda, MD, USA, 1976.
10. Balitsky, K.P.; Shuba, E.P. Resting potential of malignant tumour cells. *Acta Unio Int. Contra Cancrum* **1964**, *20*, 1391–1393.
11. Jamakosmanovic, A.; Loewenstein, W. Intracellular communication and tissue growth. III. Thyroid cancer. *J. Cell Biol.* **1968**, *38*, 556–561. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Binggelli, R.; Cameron, I.L. Cellular Potential of Normal and Cancerous Fibroblasts and Hepatocytes. *Cancer Res.* **1980**, *40*, 1830–1835.
13. Coster, H.G.L. The Physics of Cell Membranes. *J. Biol. Phys.* **2003**, *29*, 363–399. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
14. Bohinca, K.; Bossa, G.V.; May, S. Incorporation of ion and solvent structure into mean-field modeling of the electric double layer. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2017**, *249*, 220–233. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
15. Bohinc, K.; Kralj-Iglič, V.; Iglič, A. Thickness of electrical double layer. Effect of ion size. *Electrochim. Acta* **2001**, *46*, 3033–3040. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Teif, V.B.; Bohinc, K. Condensed DNA: Condensing the concepts. *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* **2011**, *105*, 208–222. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Bohinc, K.; Iglič, A.; May, S. Interaction between macroions mediated by divalent rodlike ions. *Europhys. Lett.* **2004**, *68*, 494–500. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Bohinc, K.; Shrestha, A.; Brumen, M.; May, S. Poisson-Helmholtz-Boltzmann model of the electric double layer: analysis of monovalent ionic mixtures. *Phys. Rev. E* **2012**, *85*, 031130. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Mengistu, D.H.; Bohinc, K.; May, S. Poisson-Boltzmann model in a solvent of interacting Langevin dipoles. *Europhys. Lett.* **2009**, *88*, 14003. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Caetano, D.L.; Bossa, G.V.; de Oliveira, V.M.; Brown, M.A.; de Carvalho, S.J.; May, S. Role of ion hydration for the differential capacitance of an electric double layer. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *18*, 27796–27807. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Bohinc, K.; Shrestha, A.; May, S. The Poisson-Helmholtz-Boltzmann model. *Eur. Phys. J. E Soft Matter Biol. Phys.* **2011**, *34*, 1–10. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Brown, M.A.; Bossa, G.V.; May, S. Emergence of a Stern layer from the incorporation of hydration interactions into the Gouy-Chapman model of the electrical double layer. *Langmuir* **2015**, *31*, 11477–11483. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Iglič, A.; Gongadze, E.; Bohinc, K. Excluded volume effect and orientational ordering near charged surface in solution of ions and Langevin dipoles. *Bioelectrochemistry* **2010**, *79*, 223–227. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
24. Mbamala, E.C.; Fahr, A.; May, S. Electrostatic model for mixed cationic-zwitterionic lipid bilayers. *Langmuir* **2006**, *22*, 5129–5139. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
25. Wang, M.; Chen, E.Q.; Yang, S.; May, S. Incorporating headgroup structure into the Poisson-Boltzmann model of charged lipid membranes. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *139*, 024703. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Mengistu, D.H.; May, S. Debye-Huckel theory of mixed charged-zwitterionic lipid layers. *Eur. Phys. J. E* **2008**, *26*, 251–260. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

27. Mengistu, D.H.; May, S. Nonlinear Poisson-Boltzmann model of charged lipid membranes: Accounting for the presence of zwitterionic lipids. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2008**, *129*, 121105. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
28. Bohinc, K.; Giner-Casares, J.J.; May, S. Analytic model for the dipole potential of a lipid layer. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2014**, *118*, 7568–7576. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. May, S.; Iglič, A.; Reščič, J.; Maset, S.; Bohinc, K. Bridging like-charged macroions through long divalent rodlike ions. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2008**, *112*, 1685–1692. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. May, S.; Bohinc, K. Attraction between like charged surfaces mediated by uniformly charged spherical colloids in a salt solution. *Croat. Chem. Acta* **2011**, *84*, 251–257. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Bohinc, K.; Bossa, G.V.; Gavryushov, S.; May, S. Poisson-Boltzmann model of electrolytes containing uniformly charged spherical nanoparticles. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *145*, 234901. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Uehara, M.; Sakane, K.K. Physics and Biology: Bio-plasma physics. *Am. J. Phys.* **2000**, *68*, 450. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Sundelacruz, S.; Levin, M.; Kaplan, D.L. Role of the membrane potential in the regulation of cell proliferation and differentiation. *Stem Cell Rev.* **2009**, *5*, 231–246. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Lobikin, M.; Chernet, B.; Lobo, D.; Levin, M. Resting potential, oncogene-induced tumorigenesis, and metastasis: The bioelectric basis of cancer in vivo. *Phys. Biol.* **2012**, *9*, 065002. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Schwab, A.; Fabian, A.; Hanley, P.J.; Stock, C. Role of the ion channels and transporters in cell migration. *Physiol. Rev.* **2012**, *92*, 1865–1913. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
36. Johnstone, R.M. Microelectrode penetration of ascites tumour cells. *Nature* **1959**, *183*, 411. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
37. Marino, A.A.; Morris, D.M.; Schwalke, M.A.; Iliev, I.G.; Rogers, S. Electrical potential measurements in human breast cancer and benign lesions. *Tumour Biol.* **1994**, *15*, 147–152. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Cameron, I.L.; Smith, N.K.; Pool, T.B.; Sparks, R.L. Intracellular concentration of sodium and other elements as related to mitogenesis and oncogenesis in vivo. *Cancer Res.* **1980**, *40*, 1493–1500.
39. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. How Life Works—A Continuous Seebeck-Peltier Transition in Cell Membrane? *Entropy* **2020**, *22*, 960. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Yourgrau, W.; van der Merwe, A.; Raw, G. *Treatise on Irreversible and Statistical Thermophysics*; Dover: New York, NY, USA, 1982.
41. Callen, H.B. *Thermodynamics*; Wiley: New York, NY, USA, 1960.
42. Katchalsky, A.; Curran, P.F. *Nonequilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics*; Harvard University Press: Boston, MA, USA, 1965.
43. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. Resonance in Thermal Fluxes Through Cancer Membrane. *Atti Dell'Accademia Peloritana Dei Pericolanti* **2020**, *98*, SC1–SC6. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Schrödinger, E. *What's Life? The Physical Aspect of the Living Cell*; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK, 1944.
45. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G.; Ponzetto, A.; Deisboeck, T.S. Thermodynamic considerations on the role of heat and mass transfer in biochemical causes of carcinogenesis. *Physica A* **2018**, *490*, 1164–1170. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. Second law efficiency for living cells. *Front. Biosci.* **2017**, *9*, 270–275. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
47. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. Non-equilibrium thermodynamic approach to Ca²⁺-fluxes in cancer. *Appl. Sci.* **2020**, *10*, 6737. [[CrossRef](#)]
48. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. Thermal Physics and Glaucoma: from Thermodynamic to Biophysical Considerations to Designing Future Therapies. *Appl. Sci.* **2020**, *10*, 7071. [[CrossRef](#)]
49. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G.; Kuzemsky, A.L. Time, Irreversibility and Entropy Production in Nonequilibrium Systems. *Entropy* **2020**, *22*, 887. [[CrossRef](#)]
50. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. Thermal Resonance and Cell Behavior. *Entropy* **2020**, *22*, 774. [[CrossRef](#)]
51. Rizzuto, R.; Marchi, S.; Bonora, M.; Aguiari, P.; Bononi, A.; Stefani, D.D.; Giorgi, C.; Leo, S.; Rimessi, A.; Siviero, R.; et al. Ca(2+) transfer from the ER to mitochondria: When, how and why. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* **2009**, *1787*, 1342–1351. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
52. Berridge, M.J.; Bootman, M.D.; Roderick, H.L. Calcium signalling: Dynamics, homeostasis and remodelling. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* **2003**, *4*, 517–529. [[CrossRef](#)]
53. Pinton, P.; Ferrari, D.; Rapizzi, E.; Virgilio, F.D.; Pozzan, T.; Rizzuto, R. The Ca²⁺ concentration of the endoplasmic reticulum is a key determinant of ceramide-induced apoptosis: Significance for the molecular mechanism of Bcl-2 action. *EMBO* **2001**, *20*, 2690–2701. [[CrossRef](#)]

54. Stewart, T.A.; Yapa, K.T.; Monteith, G.R. Altered calcium signaling in cancer cells. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* **2015**, *1848*, 2502–2511. [[CrossRef](#)]
55. Prigogine, I. *Etude Thermodynamique des phénomènes irréversibles*; Desoer: Liège, Belgium, 1947.
56. Milo, R.; Phillips, R. *Cell Biology by the Numbers*; Garland Science: New York, NY, USA, 2003.
57. Mercer, W.B. *Technical Manuscript 640—The Living Cell as an Open Thermodynamic System: Bacteria and Irreversible Thermodynamica*; Department of the U.S. Army—Fort Detrick: Frederic, MD, USA, 1971.
58. Borle, A.B. An Overview of Techniques for the Measurement of Calcium Distribution, Calcium Fluxes, and Cytosolic Free Calcium in Mammalian Cells. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **1990**, *84*, 45–56. [[CrossRef](#)]
59. Bonora, M.; Bononi, A.; Marchi, E.D.; Giorgi, C.; Lebedzinska, M.; Marchi, S.; Patergnani, S.; Rimessi, A.; Suski, J.M.; Wojtala, A.; et al. Role of the c subunit of the FO ATP synthase in mitochondrial permeability transition. *Cell Cycle* **2013**, *12*, 674–683. [[CrossRef](#)]
60. Šileikytė, J.; Forte, M. The Mitochondrial Permeability Transition in Mitochondrial Disorders. *Oxidative Med. Cell. Longev.* **2019**, 3403075. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
61. Bonora, M.; Wieckowski, M.R.; Chinopoulos, C.; Kepp, O.; Kroemer, G.; Galluzzi, L.; Pinton, P. Molecular mechanisms of cell death: Central implication of ATP synthase in mitochondrial permeability transition. *Oncogene* **2015**, *34*, 1475–1486. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
62. Giorgi, C.; Missiroli, S.; Patergnani, S.; Duszynski, J.; Wieckowski, M.R.; Pinton, P. Mitochondria-associated membranes: Composition, molecular mechanisms, and physiopathological implications. *Antioxid. Redox Signal.* **2015**, *22*, 995–1019. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
63. Pinton, P.; Ferrari, D.; Magalhaes, P.; Schulze-Osthoff, K.; Virgilio, F.D.; Pozzan, T.; Rizzuto, R. Reduced loading of intracellular Ca(2+) stores and downregulation of capacitative Ca(2+) influx in Bcl-2-overexpressing cells. *J. Cell Biol.* **2000**, *148*, 857–862. [[CrossRef](#)]
64. Foyouzi-Youssefi, R.; Arnaudeau, S.; Borner, C.; Kelley, W.L.; Tschopp, J.; Lew, D.P.; Demaurex, N.; Krause, K.H. Bcl-2 decreases the free Ca²⁺ concentration within the endoplasmic reticulum. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2000**, *97*, 5723–5728. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
65. Akl, H.; Vervloessem, T.; Kiviluoto, S.; Bittremieux, M.; Parys, J.B.; Smedt, H.D.; Bultynck, G. A dual role for the anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 protein in cancer: mitochondria versus endoplasmic reticulum. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* **2014**, *1843*, 2240–2252. [[CrossRef](#)]
66. Akl, H.; Bultynck, G. Altered Ca(2+) signaling in cancer cells: Proto-oncogenes and tumor suppressors targeting IP3 receptors. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* **2013**, *1835*, 180–193.
67. Marchi, S.; Marinello, M.; Bononi, A.; Bonora, M.; Giorgi, C.; Rimessi, A.; Pinton, P. Selective modulation of subtype III IP(3)R by Akt regulates ER Ca²⁺ release and apoptosis. *Cell Death Dis.* **2012**, *3*, e304. [[CrossRef](#)]
68. Giorgi, C.; Ito, K.; Lin, H.K.; Santangelo, C.; Wieckowski, M.R.; Lebedzinska, M.; Bononi, A.; Bonora, M.; Duszynski, J.; Bernardi, R.; et al. PML regulates apoptosis at endoplasmic reticulum by modulating calcium release. *Science* **2019**, *330*, 1247–1251. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Bononi, A.; Bonora, M.; Marchi, S.; Missiroli, S.; Poletti, F.; Giorgi, C.; Pandolfi, P.P.; Pinton, P. Identification of PTEN at the ER and MAMs and its regulation of Ca²⁺ signaling and apoptosis in a protein phosphatase-dependent manner. *Cell Death Differ.* **2013**, *20*, 1631–1643. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
70. Giorgi, C.; Bonora, M.; Sorrentino, G.; Missiroli, S.; Poletti, F.; Suski, J.M.; Galindo Ramirez, F.; Rizzuto, R.; Di Virgilio, F.; Zito, E.; et al. p53 at the endoplasmic reticulum regulates apoptosis in a Ca²⁺-dependent manner. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2015**, *112*, 1779–1784. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
71. Giorgi, C.; Bonora, M.; Missiroli, S.; Poletti, F.; Ramirez, F.G.; Morciano, G.; Morganti, C.; Pandolfi, P.P.; Mammano, F.; Pinton, P. Intravital imaging reveals p53-dependent cancer cell death induced by phototherapy via calcium signaling. *Oncotarget* **2015**, *6*, 1435–1445. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
72. Rimessi, A.; Marchi, S.; Patergnani, S.; Pinton, P. H-Ras-driven tumoral maintenance is sustained through caveolin-1-dependent alterations in calcium signaling. *Oncogene* **2014**, *33*, 2329–2340. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
73. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G. Constructal law and ion transfer in normal and cancer cells. *Proc. Rom. Acad. Ser. A* **2018**, *19*, 213–218.
74. Lucia, U.; Deisboeck, T.S. The importance of ion fluxes for cancer proliferation and metastasis: A thermodynamic analysis. *J. Theor. Biol.* **2018**, *445*, 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
75. Nakanishi-Matsui, M.; Sekiya, M.; Futai, R.K.N.M. The mechanism of rotating proton pumping ATPases. *BBA-Bioenergetics* **2010**, *1797*, 1343–1352. [[CrossRef](#)]

76. Stevens, T.H.; Forgac, M. Structure, function and regulation of the vacuolar (H⁺)-ATPase. *Annu. Rev. Cell. Dev. Biol.* **1997**, *13*, 779–808. [[CrossRef](#)]
77. Tuszynski, J.A.; Kurzynski, M. *Introduction to Molecular Biophysics*; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2003; pp. 383–392.
78. Lucia, U.; Ponzetto, A.; Deisboeck, T.S. A thermo-physical analysis of the proton pump vacuolar-ATPase: The constructal approach. *Sci. Rep.* **2014**, *4*, 1. [[CrossRef](#)]
79. Rudolph, M.G.; Stanfield, R.L.; Wilson, I.A. How TCRs bind MHCs, peptides, and coreceptors. *Annu. Rev. Immunol.* **2006**, *24*, 419–466. [[CrossRef](#)]
80. Strong, R.K. Asymmetric ligand recognition by the activating natural killer cell receptor NKG2D, a symmetric homodimer. *Mol. Immunol.* **2002**, *38*, 1029–1037. [[CrossRef](#)]
81. Ardito, F.; Giuliani, M.; Perrone, D.; Troiano, G.; Muzio, L.L. The crucial role of protein phosphorylation in cell signaling and its use as targeted therapy. *Int. J. Mol. Med.* **2017**, *40*, 271–280. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
82. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G.; Dolcino, D.; Astori, M.R.; Massa, E.; Ponzetto, A. Constructal approach to bio-engineering: The ocular anterior chamber temperature. *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6*, 31099. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
83. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G.; Astori, M.R. Constructal law analysis of Cl[−] transport in eyes aqueous humor. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 6856. [[CrossRef](#)]
84. Lucia, U.; Grisolia, G.; Francia, S.; Astori, M.R. Theoretical biophysical approach to cross-linking effects on eyes pressure. *Physica A* **2019**, *534*, 122163. [[CrossRef](#)]

Publisher’s Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

© 2020 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).